

Original Research

China's Direct Investment in Pakistan: A Risk Management Framework

Salma Neelofar^{1*}, Wang Sonjiang², Tamoor Azam³, Memoona Nilofar⁴, Sadia Nelofar⁵^{1,2,3,5}Department of Management Sciences and Engineering., Kunming University of Science and Technology, 727 South Jingming Road, Kunming, 650500, China⁴Department of Business Management, Karakoram International University, Ghizer Campus, Gilgit-Baltistan, 15100, Pakistan**Article history:**

Received: 24 August 2025

Accepted: 27 August 2025

Published Online: 29 August 2025

***Correspondence:**

Department, University, Address, City, Post Code, Country

How to cite this article:

Salma Neelofar, Wang Sonjiang, Tamoor Azam, Memoona Nilofar, Sadia Nelofar (2025). China's Direct Investment in Pakistan: A Risk Management Framework. *North American Academic Research*, 8(8), 118-128. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17177448>

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations. **Copyright:** ©2025 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Abstract

This paper investigates the influencing factors of China's Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Pakistan and proposes a Risk Management Framework (RMF) to attract China's FDI. With the help of a thorough study of literature, major influencing factors were identified. Regression analysis was used to figure out how the selected factors influence China's FDI in Pakistan. The results show that the impact and significance of each variable on China's FDI in Pakistan are different. Based on the results, the variables of GDP and Per Capita Income are significant at the 0.1 level in relation to China's total FDI inflow to Pakistan. While bilateral trade volume, exchange rate, infrastructure development, and demand for FDI in Pakistan are significant at the 0.05 level, they are not significant at the 0.01 level, unlike China's total FDI inflow to Pakistan. The labor force in the FDI sector in Pakistan is significant at the 0.01 level. However, the impact of the Free Trade Agreement (FTA) on China's total FDI inflow to Pakistan is not significant. Based on the results, the paper suggests a Risk Management Framework (RMF) for the policy makers. The framework involves identifying, assessing, and mitigating risks associated with the significant factors influencing FDI.

Keywords: Risk Management; Risk Management Framework; Foreign Direct Investment; China's FDI; FDI in Pakistan.

Introduction

China's investment in Pakistan indicates an essential aspect of the bilateral relationship between the nations. This strong bilateral collaboration can be traced back to the early 21st century with the launch of the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). Launched in 2013, CPEC is a well-recognized framework founded by China to connect Gwadar Port in southwestern Pakistan to China's northwestern region of Xinjiang, facilitating trade and energy flow (Hussain, 2020). China is not only investing in CPEC, but it is extending its investment to various sectors like energy, manufacturing, construction, infrastructure, and telecommunication (Ahmad et al., 2020). China's FDI has not only inspired economic growth but also helped its iron brother to improve its infrastructure. With all this exchange of benefits between these two friendly nations, there lies a set of challenges. Both countries are confronting environmental, security, political, and economic issues (Hayat et al., 2025). Keeping in mind all these issues and challenges, there is a dire need for effective

risk management strategies to prevent hurdles.

There is an escalating demand for the risk management of China's direct investment in Pakistan within a wider context of an enhanced economy and improved infrastructure. China has proved itself as a major global economic player; its widespread investments under initiatives like the CPEC have become emblematic of a new era of economic interdependence between nations. The importance of this study lies in its ability to unravel the knots around these kinds of cross-border investments and provide an understanding of the workings of economic alliances between a major power and a developing country in a vital location. The top priority of this study is to understand and effectively manage the risks inherent in this economic collaboration. Delving into the economic risk factors and mitigation strategies, it provides a roadmap for policymakers, investors, and academics to navigate the intricacies of international investments.

Furthermore, highlighting the mutually advantageous relationship between developed and developing countries, our study intended to add to the nature of global economic power systems. The conclusions of the study do not have consequences for both countries but also for other nations participating in comparable economic relationships, as China's investments are changing Pakistan's economic environment. The research is also important because it may help with international collaboration, strategic decision-making, and the long-term growth of the countries that are part of these complex economic alliances.

Our objective for this study was to identify and analyze a comprehensive range of risk factors associated with China's direct investment in Pakistan and suggest a risk management framework.

Materials and Methods

Through a thorough study of literature, we selected some critical factors of FDI such as the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Pakistan, the total bilateral trade between China and Pakistan, exchange rates, the host country's demand for FDI, infrastructure construction, and the quantity of FDI labor are the main factors affecting FDI between the two countries. As various organizations promoting trade cooperation have emerged internationally, these organizations can also promote trade between China and Pakistan, which will have an impact on bilateral FDI. Therefore, this paper selects China's total FDI in Pakistan as the dependent variable and the various influencing factors as independent variables to establish the following regression analysis model:

$$\ln EX_{ij} = c + \beta_1 \ln GDP_j + \beta_2 \ln P_j + \beta_3 \ln TAVO_i + \beta_4 \ln R_{ij} + \beta_5 \ln AGP_i + \beta_6 \ln FD_j + \beta_7 \ln FTA + \beta_8 \ln AGL_i + \epsilon$$

Where: 1, 2..., 8 represent coefficients, c represents a constant term, and ϵ represents the random error term.

Data Source

The annual data on China's FDI in Pakistan from 1995 to 2022 are obtained from the Pakistan Statistical Yearbook. The stationarity of the data is tested using the ADF test. The cointegration test is then performed to analyze the direct relationship between China's FDI and trade in goods with Pakistan in the context of the Belt and Road Initiative. The main data used in this study is derived from the World Bank data for the years 1995 to 2022, supplemented with trade data from Pakistan.

Variable Selection and Explanation

Based on previous research, several factors have been identified as key determinants of FDI between China and Pakistan, including Pakistan's GDP, total bilateral trade between China and Pakistan, exchange rates, host country demand for FDI, infrastructure development, and the number of FDI-related labor force. Additionally, international organizations promoting trade cooperation can also have an impact on FDI between China and Pakistan. Therefore, the selected indicators for this study include

Variable	Variable Meaning
EX _{ij}	Dependent Variable: FDI Total Volume from China to Pakistan
	Independent Variables
GDP _j	GDP of Pakistan
P _j	Per capita income of Pakistan
TAVO _i	Bilateral trade volume between China and Pakistan
R _{ij}	Exchange rate of Pakistani currency to Chinese Renminbi
AGP _i	Infrastructure development in Pakistan
FD _j	Demand for FDI in Pakistan
FTA	China-Pakistan Free Trade Zone
AGL _i	Labor force in Pakistan

Table 1: Variable Definitions

Variable Explanation:

EX_{ij}: This is the dependent variable in this study, representing the FDI value from China to Pakistan.

GDP_j: This variable is the independent variable, primarily the GDP of Pakistan, which reflects the national economic situation of Pakistan, derived from data from the United Nations Statistical Yearbook.

P_j: This variable represents the per capita GDP of Pakistan, serving as a proxy for the consumption capacity of the Pakistani people, obtained from the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics.

TAVO_i: Total bilateral trade between China and Pakistan, reflecting Pakistan's ability in goods export, represented by the total value of bilateral trade in goods between China and Pakistan.

R_{ij}: We adopt the exchange rate of the Pakistani Rupee to the Chinese Renminbi, using the US Dollar as an intermediate conversion unit. The exchange rate can serve as a barrier to trade between the two countries.

AGP_i: Pakistan's infrastructure development, reflecting the ease of domestic investment. This study takes the investment amount in Pakistan's infrastructure construction as an indicator, sourced from the Ministry of Commerce of Pakistan.

FD_j: The demand for FDI in Pakistan which determines the amount of foreign investment that Pakistan needs to attract. This demand may vary due to natural or other factors.

FTA: This variable is a dummy variable representing the establishment of a free trade zone. The construction of a free trade zone makes it easier for Pakistan to attract foreign investment, promoting FDI inflows.

AGL_i: The number of labor forces related to FDI in Pakistan, which reflects the supply level of FDI. By analyzing the above variables, the main research model influencing China's FDI in Pakistan under the Belt and Road Initiative is as follows:

$$\ln EX_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln GDP_j + \beta_2 \ln P_j + \beta_3 \ln TAVO_i + \beta_4 \ln R_{ij} + \beta_5 \ln AGP_i + \beta_6 \ln FD_j + \beta_7 \ln FTA + \beta_8 \ln AGL_i + \mu_t$$

Results and Discussions

Correlation Analysis

In the analysis, the correlation coefficient "r" is often used to represent the correlation between variables. If the calculated "r" value is less than 0, it indicates a negative correlation between the variables. If the value is 0, it means there is no correlation between the variables. If the value is greater than 0, it shows a positive correlation between the variables. Furthermore, the magnitude of the "r" value indicates the degree of correlation. When the value is greater than 0.8, it indicates a strong correlation between the variables. When the value is in the range of (0.5, 0.8), it suggests a significant correlation. When the value is in the range of (0.3, 0.5), it indicates a low-density correlation. If the value is less than 0.3, it means the variables are not correlated.

Absolute Correlation Coefficient (r)	Degree of Correlation
<0.3	Not correlated
0.3-0.5	Low correlation

0.5-0.8	Moderate correlation
>0.8	High correlation

Table 2: Interpretation of absolute correlation coefficient values.

The results of the correlation analysis in this paper are as follows:

	GDPj	pi	TAVOi	Rij	AGPi	FDj	AGP	FTA	AGli	Exij
GDPj	1									
Pj	0.066	1								
TAVOi	0.006	0.442	1							
Rij	0.002	0.415	0.552	1						
AGPi	0.001	0.596	0.564	0.474	1					
FDj	0.683	0.424	-0.266	0.468	0.477	0.575	1			
FTA	0.555	0.266	0.472	0.368	0.458	0.482	0.585	1		
AGLi	0.455	0.311	0.375	0.576	0.555	0.364	0.286	0.585	1	
Exij	0.467	0.673	0.877	0.837	0.806	0.865	0.888	0.466	0.857	1

Table 3: Correlation Coefficient Table

In the correlation analysis of the original data, it can be observed that the variables with a closer relationship to China's FDI in Pakistan are the bilateral trade volume between China and Pakistan (TAVOi), the exchange rate of Pakistan's currency to the Chinese yuan (Rij), Pakistan's infrastructure construction (AGPi), Pakistan's demand for FDI (FDj), and the quantity of labor force (AGLi). However, the correlation coefficient of per capita GDP is only 0.672, indicating that this variable has relatively low correlation compared to others. Analyzing the correlation of variables based on the original data can provide preliminary insights, but further investigation is required to determine if there is a clear correlation between these variables and the dependent variable.

Unit Root Test for Data Stationarity

If a series has unit roots, it indicates non-stationarity. Therefore, it is necessary to test whether the series is long-term stable by detecting the presence of unit roots. There are three methods for unit root testing: the Dickey-Fuller (DF) test, the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, and the Phillips-Perron (PP) test. The commonly used method is the ADF test, which is an extension of the DF test developed by Dickey (1979) and Fuller (1980). The ADF test incorporates lag terms to control for higher-order serial correlations. The model is constructed as follows:

$$\Delta X_t = \alpha + \beta_t + \gamma X_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \Theta_i * \Delta X_{t-1} + \varepsilon$$

Where X_t , $X_t - X_{t-1}$, α are constant terms, t is a trend term, p is the optimal lag length, and ε is the random error term. The hypothesis test is conducted as follows:

$$H_0: \gamma = 0; \quad H_1: \gamma < 0$$

If the test results indicate $H_0: < 0$, it means that the sequence is non-stationary. If the test results indicate $H_1: < 0$, it suggests that the sequence is stationary and passes the test. If the sequence is found to be non-stationary, it needs to be differenced multiple times to form an n -order integrated sequence. The determination of integration is based on how many times the sequence becomes stationary after differencing. If the series remains non-stationary after $n-1$ differences, then it can be considered an n -order integrated sequence. It is denoted as $I(n)$. In this study, before conducting regression analysis, the stationarity of the sequence needs to be examined using the ADF test to check for the presence of unit roots. The test results are as follows:

Variable	Lag Order	ADF Test	ADF Critical Values		10%	Stationarity
			1%	5%		

							Decisio
							n
LN(GDPj)	Original Series	0	-0.652	-3.988	-3.217	-2.673	NO
	Second-order Difference	1	-3.345	-4.127	-3.117	-3.013	YES
LN(Pj)	Original Series	0	-1.232	-4.128	-3.463	-3.332	NO
	Second-order Difference	1	-3.422	-4.872	-3.257	-3.113	YES
LN(TAVOi)	Original Series	0	-3.264	-4.567	-3.622	-3.312	NO
	Second-order Difference	1	-4.234	-4.275	-3.116	-3.005	YES
LN(Rij)	Original Series	0	-2.624	-4.188	-3.227	-3.202	NO
	Second-order Difference	1	-2.635	-4.563	-3.577	-2.226	YES
LN(AGPi)	Original Series	0	-2.636	-4.648	-3.277	-3.117	NO
	Second-order Difference	1	-4.236	-4.877	-3.279	-3.007	YES
LN(FDj)	Original Series	0	-1.316	-4.277	-3.118	-3.002	NO
	Second-order Difference	1	-5.166	-4.654	-3.275	-3.212	YES
LN(FTA)	Original Series	0	-3.063	-4.728	-3.479	-3.332	NO
	Second-order Difference	1	-3.762	-4.188	-3.272	-3.188	YES
LN(AGLi)	Original Series	0	-2.875	-4.337	-3.552	-3.429	NO
	Second-order Difference	1	-4.673	-4.525	-3.279	-3.108	YES

Table 4: Unit root test results

From the test results, it can be observed that the original sequence without second-order differencing is non-stationary. Only after differencing does the sequence exhibit stationary characteristics. Therefore, the sequence is considered an order of integrated series, passing the stationarity test.

4.5.3 Cointegration Test

Cointegration analysis is primarily used to determine if variables that are not significant in the short term have a significant relationship over a longer period. The "EG" two-step method is commonly employed for this purpose, which was proposed by Engle and Granger and is the cointegration test method used in this study. In the first step, the variables are regressed using the least squares method:

$$X_t = \alpha + \beta_i Y_t + \varepsilon_t$$

The second step involves checking the stationarity of the residuals. The ADF test is used to examine the stationarity of the residual series. If the test results indicate stationarity, it implies that the variable is long-term stable. Conversely, if the results indicate non-stationarity, it suggests that the variable is long-term unstable and does not exhibit cointegration. In this study, the ADF test is first performed to determine if TAVOi (bilateral trade volume between China and Pakistan), Rij (exchange rate of the Pakistani currency against the Chinese yuan), AGPi (Pakistan's infrastructure development), FDj (demand for FDI in Pakistan), and AGLi (number of labor force in Pakistan) are integrated of the same order as EXij (Pakistan's FDI inflow). Testing the integration of these variables is a prerequisite for examining their cointegration. If all six variables are found to be integrated, the cointegration of their residuals can be examined using the two-step approach. If not, the two-step approach cannot be applied. In the previous discussion, it has been demonstrated that all variables are of the same integrated order. Therefore, the following model is established to test the cointegration of the residuals.

$$\ln(EX)_t = \alpha + \beta \ln(TAVOi)_t + \varepsilon_t$$

$$\ln(EX)_t = \alpha + \beta \ln(Rij)_t + \varepsilon_t$$

$$\ln(EX)_t = \alpha + \beta \ln(AGPi)_t + \varepsilon_t$$

$$\ln(EX)_t = \alpha + \beta \ln(FDj)_t + \varepsilon_t$$

$$\ln(EX)_t = \alpha + \beta \ln(AGLi)_t + \varepsilon_t$$

The following table presents the cointegration test results for these 5 variables:

Residuals	Lag Order	ADF Test Value	ADF Test Value 1%	ADF Test Value 5%	ADF Test Value 10%	Stationarity Decision
TAVO _i : ϵ t	1	-3.493	-3.958	-3.082	-2.682	yes
R: ϵ t	1	-2.914	-3.958	-3.005	-2.568	yes
AGP _i : ϵ tFDj: ϵ tAGLi: ϵ t	1	-6.615	-4.801	-3.792	-3.433	yes
	1	-5.234	-4.129	-3.113	-3.119	yes
	1	-3.173	-4.223	-3.009	-2.996	yes

Table 5: Cointegration Test Results

From Table 5, it can be observed that there is a long-term stable equilibrium relationship between bilateral trade volume TAVO_i, exchange rate R_{ij}, infrastructure development AGP_i, demand for FDI FD_j, and labor force quantity AGL_i in Pakistan and China's total FDI inflow to Pakistan (EX_{ij}).

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	T-Statistic	Prob.
LN(GDP _j)	0.002	0.025	1.645	0.084*
LN(P _j)	0.533	0.092	1.725	0.092*
LN(TAVO _i)	0.304	0.665	-1.448	0.0234**
LN(R)	1.195	2.696	2.225	0.0207**
LN(AGP _i)	4.207	1.414	-2.342	0.0212**
LN(FD _j)	0.307	0.204	2.002	0.0329**
LN(FTA)	0.174	0.047	1.293	0.4023
LN(AGL _i)	0.568	0.057	3.787	0.0067***

Note: * represents P<0.1; ** represents P<0.05; *** represents P<0.01.

Table 6: Model Regression Results

From the results, it can be observed that the impact and significance of each variable on China's FDI in Pakistan are different. Based on the results, the variables of GDP_j (Gross Domestic Product) and P_j (Per Capita Income) are significant at the 0.1 level about China's total FDI inflow to Pakistan (EX_{ij}). Specifically, for every 1 unit increase in Pakistan's GDP, China's direct investment in Pakistan increases by 0.084 units. This is mainly because the growth of Pakistan's domestic economy brings about changes in the investment environment and conditions, making it more convenient to attract direct investment from China (Igbal, 2025).

Furthermore, variables such as bilateral trade volume TAVO_i, exchange rate R_{ij}, infrastructure development AGP_i, and demand for FDI FD_j in Pakistan are significant at the 0.05 level about China's total FDI inflow to Pakistan (EX_{ij}). Additionally, the variable of labor force AGL_i in the FDI sector in Pakistan is significant at the 0.01 level. However, the impact of the Free Trade Agreement (FTA) on China's total FDI inflow to Pakistan (EX_{ij}) is not significant.

Risk Management Framework (RMF)

RMF is an organized approach to identifying, evaluating, prioritizing, and mitigating risks that could impact an organization's goals or operations. It usually consists of a collection of policies, procedures, processes, and tools intended to methodically manage risks across an organization or in a particular context (Jeong et al., 2023).

The steps of the Risk Management framework.

Risk Identification

Figure 1: Steps of risk Management

Once we figured out the significance of the factors selected for the study, we had a clear idea of the factors that are crucial for China's FDI in Pakistan. Our Framework for the risk management of China's FDI in Pakistan is as follows:

Figure 2: Framework

Risk Identification

Risk identification is the first step in the RMF (Nobanee, 2021). As per our results, the significant factors are Gross Domestic Product (**GDP_j**), Per Capita Income (**P_j**), bilateral trade volume (**TAVO_i**), the exchange rate (**R_{ij}**), infrastructure development (**AGP_i**), and demand for FDI (**FD_j**). We have noticed that there was a significant increase in China's FDI, with a certain amount of increase in the value of these factors. Hence, the risk related to these factors is a decrease in the value of these factors, which may harm China's FDI in Pakistan. Some risks, for example, related to each factor, are presented in the given table.

Factor	Possible Risk	Possible Impact
GDP	Economic Downturn	Adverse impact on FDI attractiveness
Per Capita Income	Decrease in Purchasing power	Adverse impact on Consumer demand and Market Potential
Bilateral Trade Volume	Trade disputes and restrictions	Adverse Impact on Investment Climate
Exchange Rate	Currency Volatility	Adverse impact on investment returns
Infrastructure Development	Insufficient infrastructure	Adverse impact on Business operations
Demand for FDI	Decrease in demand due to regulatory changes and geopolitical tensions	Adverse impact on FDI

Table 7: Risk Assessment

Risk Assessment

The second phase is to evaluate each risk's probability of happening and its possible effects on China's foreign direct investment in Pakistan. For this purpose, both qualitative and quantitative methods can be employed (Animah & Shafiee, 2020). Another method is to assess the overall severity of risks by employing probability-impact matrices (Bakhtawar et al., 2021). This includes calculating each risk's impact and likelihood of occurrence on a matrix. Another better strategy is utilizing risk-scoring tools (Ugliotti et al., 2023; Abergos & Madjek, 2024). These methods provide numerical ratings of the probability of each risk's occurrence and its possible effect, allowing a more quantitative evaluation of the risk's possible influence on China's foreign direct investment in Pakistan.

Mitigation strategy

The probable strategy to lessen risks related to each decisive factor can be:

GDP_j: As shown in Table 6, 1% increase in the GDP of the country is associated with a 0.002% increase in China's total FDI inflow to Pakistan. Therefore, Policies that will increase buying power and stimulate economic growth should be put into action (Chugunov et al., 2021). Such as tax breaks, spending on healthcare and education, and encouraging entrepreneurship. Further, Pakistan should invest in CPEC industrial zones to leverage GDP in the areas that are FDI-sensitive, for instance, textiles, autos, etc. This way, the risk of economic downturn can be potentially contained, and the attraction of China's FDI in Pakistan can be greatly enhanced.

LN(P_j): The impact is weakly positive as there is 1% increase in Pakistan's per capita income; the ratio of increase in China's FDI is 0.533%. Hence, to mitigate the possible risk of a decrease in purchasing power and its adverse impact on consumer demand and market Potential, Pakistan should boost its disposable income by job creation in and around CPEC zones to fascinate consumer-focused Chinese FDI. Additionally, Pakistan should target investments in affordable goods and services for the middle class.

TAVO_i and R_{ij}: By hedging against currency swings, entering into forward contracts, and, when practical, conducting transactions in local currencies, investors may diversify their investment portfolios and reduce their exposure to trade and currency risks. Additionally, work on bilateral agreements to lower trade obstacles and stable currency rates (Stoykova, 2021; Solonenko, 2024).

AGP_i: Invest in partnerships or infrastructure development initiatives to enhance market accessibility, logistics, and connectivity. Public-private partnerships, foreign investment in vital infrastructure sectors, and focused development initiatives to fill infrastructure gaps might all be part of this.

FD_j: Streamline regulatory procedures, offer incentives to international investors, and cultivate a business-friendly atmosphere to bolster investment promotion initiatives. To encourage foreign direct investment (FDI), this may entail expediting permit approvals, lowering administrative barriers, and providing tax benefits or investment incentives (Zhang & Li, 2024). Engage in focused marketing initiatives as well to draw attention to investment possibilities and emphasize the advantages of investing in Pakistan.

Monitor and Review

The subsequent phase of the Risk Management Framework (RMF) places great importance on monitoring and review (Al-Wathinani et al., 2023). Here, a strong monitoring system is set up to track the efficacy of risk reduction tactics as they are put into practice. This entails routinely evaluating whether the mitigation strategies are producing the intended effects and whether the identified risks are being appropriately handled. In the monitoring and review step, the risk landscape is routinely reviewed proactively. This entails determining any new dangers that might not have been recognized before and estimating how they would affect China's foreign direct investment in Pakistan. Policymakers may continue to safeguard investment by modifying the risk management approach as needed by being proactive and alert to changes in the risk environment.

Risk Communication

Despite its enormous importance, this RMF stage is generally overlooked (Goerlandt, Li, & Reniers, 2020; Lahiri & Saltz, 2024). It is crucial to carry out the RMF process by informing the appropriate department, including policymakers and decision-makers, about risk information, the possible effect of risk, and mitigation solutions.

Risk Governance

Establishing precise roles, duties, and accountability frameworks is the first step in ensuring efficient risk management in the context of policymaking (Li & Li, 2021). It is crucial to assign particular people or groups the task of supervising risk management initiatives and guaranteeing that suitable actions are taken to mitigate hazards that have been identified.

Policymakers may guarantee that all pertinent parties are aware of their duties in efficiently managing risks by providing clear definitions of roles and responsibilities. This involves designating the proper people or departments to handle duties, including risk identification, assessment, mitigation, and monitoring.

Compliance and Reporting

In order to reduce legal and regulatory risks, risk management must ensure compliance with applicable laws, rules, and standards. This entails keeping abreast of the laws and rules that apply to commerce, finance, investing, and other pertinent fields. Conducting routine audits, evaluations, and reviews to make sure that legal requirements are being followed is an example of compliance initiatives.

Transparency and accountability also require that risk management performance be reported to the appropriate stakeholders (Effuniyi et al., 2024). This entails informing stakeholders, including governmental organizations, financial institutions, and the general public, about important risk management initiatives, discoveries, and results. Periodic reports, presentations, or disclosures that offer information on risk management performance and practices are examples of reporting systems.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in order for policymakers to successfully reduce possible risks, they must create a thorough risk management framework (RMF) that is customized to the unique environment of luring China's Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Pakistan. Policymakers can pinpoint areas of vulnerability and put targeted risk mitigation strategies into place by analyzing the key factors influencing China's FDI, such as GDP, PCI, bilateral trade volume, exchange rate, infrastructure development, and demand for FDI.

There are several crucial phases in the suggested RMF. First of all, by classifying and ranking the risks connected to each important component, policymakers may concentrate their efforts on resolving the most pressing issues. Second, evaluating these risks' impact and likelihood using qualitative or quantitative techniques offers important information on how they could affect China's foreign direct investment in Pakistan. Thirdly, the possibility and effect of identified risks may be decreased by putting mitigation techniques into practice, such as developing infrastructure, diversifying investment portfolios, reforming economic policy, and expediting regulatory procedures.

In addition, the implementation of monitoring and evaluation procedures facilitates the ability of policymakers to evaluate the efficacy of risk reduction tactics and modify them as necessary in light of evolving conditions. Furthermore, defining precise roles, duties, and accountability frameworks guarantees the effective and efficient execution of risk management operations. Ultimately, transparent reporting on risk management performance and adherence to pertinent laws, rules, and standards builds confidence and trust among stakeholders.

Policymakers in Pakistan may more effectively manage the risks involved in luring China's FDI by adhering to this RMF, which would eventually promote an atmosphere that is favorable to investment and economic expansion. To effectively handle new difficulties and possibilities in the ever-changing world of foreign investment, risk management is a continuous process that needs constant monitoring, assessment, and adaptation. Thus, in order to optimize the advantages of China's FDI while lowering possible hazards, officials should continue to be watchful and aggressive in their risk management efforts. (10

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Abergos VJ, Medjek F. A risk assessment analysis to enhance the security of OT WAN with SD-WAN. *J Cyber Secur Priv.* 2024;4(4):910-37.
- [2] Ahmad R, Mi H, Fernald LW. Revisiting the potential security threats linked with the China–Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). *J Int Coun Small Bus.* 2020;1(1):64-80.
- [3] Akbar M, Akbar A. An empirical analysis of foreign direct investment in Pakistan. *Stud Bus Econ.* 2015;10(1):5-15.
- [4] Al-Wathinani AM, Barten DG, Borowska-Stefańska M, Gołda P, AlDulijan NA, Alhallaf MA, et al. Driving sustainable disaster risk reduction: A rapid review of the policies and strategies in Saudi Arabia. *Sustainability.* 2023;15(14):10976.
- [5] Animah I, Shafiee M. Application of risk analysis in the liquefied natural gas (LNG) sector: An overview. *J Loss Prev Process Ind.* 2020;63:103980.
- [6] Arslan SM, Kanwal A, Kazmi SMFA, Rahman SU. The Impact of Institutional Performance and Environmental Sustainability on Foreign Direct Investment in Pakistan. *iRASD J Econ.* 2023;5(4):944-65.
- [7] Bahamid RA, Doh SI, Khoiry MA, Kassem MA, Al-Sharafi MA. The Current Risk Management Practices and Knowledge in the Construction Industry. *Buildings.* 2022;12(7):1016.
- [8] Bakhtawar B, Thaheem MJ, Arshad H, Tariq S, Mazher KM, Zayed T, et al. A sustainability-based risk assessment for P3 projects using a simulation approach. *Sustainability.* 2021;14(1):344.
- [9] Buckley PJ, Chen L, Clegg LJ, Voss H. Experience and FDI risk-taking: A microfoundational reconceptualization. *J Int Manag.* 2016;22(2):131-46.
- [10] Buckley PJ, Chen L, Clegg LJ, Voss H. The role of endogenous and exogenous risk in FDI entry choices. *J World Bus.* 2020;55(1):101040.
- [11] Chugunov I, Pasichnyi M, Koroviy V, Kaneva T, Nikitishin A. Fiscal and monetary policy of economic development. *Eur J Sustain Dev.* 2021;10(1):42.
- [12] Damodaran A. *Country Risk: Determinants, Measures and Implications-The 2025 Edition.* 2025.
- [13] Eller M, Hauzenberger N, Huber F, Schuberth H, Vashold L. The impact of macroprudential policies on capital flows in CESEE. *J Int Money Finance.* 2021;119:102495.
- [14] Fania N, Yan C, Kuyon JB, Djeri S. Geopolitical risks (GPRs) and foreign direct investments: A business risk approach. *Glob J Manag Bus Res.* 2020;20(1):1-9.
- [15] Goerlandt F, Li J, Reniers G. The landscape of risk communication research: A scientometric analysis. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(9):3255.
- [16] Hayat S, Khalil NUK, Rizwan M, Butt S. Pakistan Foreign Policy Dynamics: Exploring The Interplay of CPEC, Energy Security, Environmental Concerns and Diplomatic Engagements. *Soc Sci Rev Arch.* 2025;3(3):150-77.
- [17] Hosseini H. An economic theory of FDI: A behavioral economics and historical approach. *J Socio Econ.* 2005;34(4):528-41.
- [18] Hussain F. Geostrategic Imperatives of Gwadar Port for China. *Korean J Int Stud.* 2020;18(2):145-67.
- [19] Iqbal S. The FDI Regime in Pakistan. *Bus Law Int.* 2025;26(1):49-64A.
- [20] Jamsheed RA. FDI, Foreign Debt, and Economic Growth: The South Asian Perspective (1980-2020). *J World Econ Transform Trans.* 2024;3(7).
- [21] Khaskheli MB, Wang S, Yan X, He Y. Innovation of the Social Security, Legal Risks, Sustainable Management Practices and Employee Environmental Awareness in The China–Pakistan Economic Corridor. *Sustainability.* 2023;15(2):1021.
- [22] Lahiri S, Saltz J. The need for a risk management framework for data science projects: a systematic literature review. *Int J Inf Syst Proj Manag.* 2024;12(4):41-57.
- [23] Li H, Li J. Risk Governance and Sustainability: A Scientometric Analysis and Literature Review. *Sustainability.* 2021;13(21):12015.
- [24] Nobanee H, Al Hamadi FY, Abdulaziz FA, Abukarsh LS, Alqahtani AF, AlSubaey SK, et al. A bibliometric analysis of sustainability and risk management. *Sustainability.* 2021;13(6):3277.
- [25] Oh CH, Shin J, Oetzel J. How does experience change firms' foreign investment decisions to non-market

events?. *J Int Manag.* 2021;27(1):100802.

[26] Solonenko A. The role of currency unions in promoting economic stability and integration. 2024:248.

[27] Stoykova OI. How to increase the value of bilateral trade? Currency union versus fixed exchange rate regime. *Entrep Bus Econ Rev.* 2021;9(2):21-38.

[28] Uddin M, Chowdhury A, Zafar S, Shafique S, Liu J. Institutional determinants of inward FDI: Evidence from Pakistan. *Int Bus Rev.* 2019;28(2):344-58.

[29] Ugliotti FM, Osello A, Daud M, Yilmaz OO. Enhancing Risk Analysis toward a Landscape Digital Twin Framework: A Multi-Hazard Approach in the Context of a Socio-Economic Perspective. *Sustainability.* 2023;15(16):12429.

[30] Wang R. Safeguarding enterprise prosperity: An in-depth analysis of financial management strategies. *J Knowl Econ.* 2024;15(4):17676-704.

[31] Zhang S, Li N. Addressing Climate Change through International Investment Agreements: Obstacles and Reform Options. *Sustainability.* 2024;16(4):1471.

